

Role of Higher Education Institutions in Fostering Entrepreneurship in Viksit Bharat 2047

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19136642>

Abstract:

The vision of *Viksit Bharat 2047* aims to transform India into a developed nation driven by innovation, knowledge, and sustainable economic growth by the centenary of its independence. Entrepreneurship plays a critical role in achieving this goal as it encourages innovation, generates employment opportunities, and contributes to economic resilience. (Audretsch D. B., 2012) Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) play a significant role in nurturing entrepreneurial thinking among students through entrepreneurship education, training programs, incubation facilities, and industry collaboration. This study examines the role of HEIs in promoting entrepreneurial activities among students. Primary data were collected from 26 respondents through a structured questionnaire. Descriptive statistical tools were used to analyze perceptions regarding entrepreneurship education, institutional support, and entrepreneurial intentions. The findings suggest that entrepreneurship education enhances students' confidence to start new ventures, while institutional support mechanisms such as incubation centers and mentorship programs moderately influence entrepreneurial motivation. The study recommends strengthening institutional infrastructure, improving funding mechanisms, and enhancing industry partnerships so that HEIs can contribute more effectively to achieving the national vision of *Viksit Bharat 2047*.

Keywords: Entrepreneurship, Higher Education Institutions, Innovation, Startup Ecosystem, *Viksit Bharat 2047*, Entrepreneurship Education

1. Introduction

(Shane, 2003) Entrepreneurship is widely recognized as an important driver of economic development, technological progress, and employment creation in modern economies. (Audretsch, Entrepreneurship research., 2012) Countries that encourage entrepreneurial activities often experience faster economic growth and greater innovation capacity. India's development vision, known as *Viksit Bharat 2047*, focuses on building a knowledge-based and innovation-driven economy that promotes entrepreneurship, technological advancement, and sustainable development.

(Etzkowitz, 2008) In this transformation process, Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) play a vital role in developing entrepreneurial competencies among students and researchers. Universities and colleges are increasingly evolving beyond their traditional roles of teaching and research to become centers of innovation and startup development. Educational reforms and policy initiatives have further strengthened this shift toward entrepreneurship-oriented education.

(India, 2020) The National Education Policy 2020 encourages multidisciplinary learning, experiential education, and the commercialization of research outcomes. Similarly, initiatives such as Startup India and Atal Innovation Mission have been introduced to promote innovation, startup culture, and entrepreneurial ecosystems across the country.

HEIs contribute to entrepreneurship development through entrepreneurship-focused curricula, incubation centers, mentorship programs, and industry partnerships. These initiatives help students transform innovative ideas into viable business ventures, thereby contributing to economic development and employment generation. Therefore, examining the role of higher education institutions in fostering entrepreneurship is essential for understanding their contribution toward achieving the vision of *Viksit Bharat 2047*.

2. Objectives of the Study

1. To examine the role of Higher Education Institutions in encouraging entrepreneurship.
2. To evaluate institutional support mechanisms available for startup development.
3. To analyze students' entrepreneurial intentions and confidence levels.
4. To suggest measures for strengthening the contribution of HEIs toward the vision of *Viksit Bharat 2047*.

3. Scope of the Study

The study focuses on students and faculty members from higher education institutions, particularly in commerce and management disciplines. It examines the influence of entrepreneurship education, institutional infrastructure, mentorship support, and policy awareness on the development of entrepreneurial intentions among students. The research is limited to respondents from higher education institutions.

4. Research Methodology

The present study follows a **descriptive research design** to examine perceptions regarding the promotion of entrepreneurship within higher education institutions.

Sources of Data

Primary Data:

Primary data were collected using a structured questionnaire based on a five-point Likert scale.

Secondary Data:

Secondary data were obtained from academic journals, books, policy documents, and government reports related to entrepreneurship and higher education.

Sample Size

The study includes 26 respondents.

Sampling Technique

Convenience sampling was used to select respondents for the study.

Statistical Tools Used

- Percentage analysis
- Mean score analysis

The Likert scale ranged from 1 (Strongly Disagree) to 5 (Strongly Agree).

5. Data Analysis and Interpretation

Entrepreneurship Education

The analysis shows that respondents moderately agree that their institutions offer courses related to entrepreneurship, with a mean score of **3.35**. Similarly, the statement that the curriculum encourages innovation recorded a mean score of **3.38**, indicating a moderate focus on innovation-oriented learning.

Experiential learning methods such as projects and case studies received a mean score of **3.62**, suggesting that practical learning approaches effectively contribute to entrepreneurial skill

development. Encouragement for entrepreneurship across different academic disciplines obtained a mean score of **3.58**, reflecting positive institutional support for entrepreneurial activities.

Institutional Support and Infrastructure

(Etzkowitz., 2008) Institutional infrastructure plays an important role in supporting entrepreneurship. The availability of incubation centers recorded a mean score of **3.15**, suggesting moderate availability of such facilities in the institutions studied.

Mentorship support for startup ideas received a mean score of **3.50**, indicating that mentoring systems exist but can be strengthened further. Financial assistance and seed capital opportunities recorded a lower mean score of **3.04**, suggesting that access to startup funding remains a challenge for many students.

Industry collaboration for startup support obtained a mean score of **3.00**, indicating moderate interaction between academic institutions and industry partners.

Policy Awareness and Entrepreneurial Ecosystem

Awareness of national startup initiatives among respondents recorded a mean score of **3.19**, indicating moderate awareness levels. Institutional policies aligning with national development goals obtained a mean score of **3.27**.

Government schemes supporting entrepreneurship recorded a mean score of **3.23**, indicating that respondents believe such initiatives moderately support entrepreneurial activities within educational institutions.

Entrepreneurial Intention and Outcomes

The intention to start a business among respondents was relatively strong. The statement “I intend to start my own venture in the future” recorded a mean score of **3.73**, reflecting positive entrepreneurial aspirations among students.

Entrepreneurship education improving confidence to start a business received the **highest mean score of 4.00**, indicating strong agreement among respondents. Institutional support increasing the likelihood of startup success recorded a mean score of **3.65**.

Furthermore, respondents agreed that HEIs play an important role in achieving the vision of Viksit Bharat 2047 through entrepreneurship, with a mean score of **3.54**.

6. Findings

- Higher education institutions moderately promote entrepreneurship through academic programs and training.
- Experiential learning approaches significantly enhance entrepreneurial skills.
- Mentorship and institutional guidance positively influence entrepreneurial confidence among students.
- Limited access to funding remains a major challenge for student entrepreneurs.
- Industry–institution collaboration needs improvement to support startup development.
- Students demonstrate strong interest in entrepreneurship and startup creation.
- Respondents believe HEIs can play an important role in achieving the vision of *Viksit Bharat 2047*.

7. Conclusion

(Audretsch, 2012) Higher Education Institutions play a vital role in promoting entrepreneurship and innovation in India. By providing entrepreneurship education, experiential learning opportunities, mentorship support, and incubation facilities, HEIs help cultivate entrepreneurial thinking among students

The results of this study indicate that entrepreneurship education significantly improves students' confidence and motivation to start new ventures. However, institutional support systems such as funding opportunities, incubation infrastructure, and industry partnerships require further development.

Strengthening these mechanisms will help universities transform into innovation hubs that generate successful startups and technological solutions. Developing strong entrepreneurial ecosystems within higher education institutions can accelerate innovation, create employment opportunities, and support economic growth. These efforts will play an important role in achieving the national vision of *Viksit Bharat 2047*, enabling India to become a developed and globally competitive economy.

References

1. Audretsch, D. B. (2012). Entrepreneurship research. *Management Decision*, 755–764.
2. Audretsch, D. B. (2012). Entrepreneurship research. *Management Decision*, 755–764.
3. Audretsch, D. B. (2012). Entrepreneurship research. *Management Decision*, 755–764.
4. Drucker, P. F. (1985). *Innovation and entrepreneurship: Practice and principles*. Harper & Row.
5. Etzkowitz, H. (2008). *The Triple Helix: University–Industry–Government innovation in action*. Routledge.
6. Etzkowitz, H. (2008). *The Triple Helix: University–industry–government innovation in action*. Routledge.
7. India, G. o. (2020). *National Education Policy 2020 Ministry of Education, Government of India*.
8. India, G. o. (2020). *National Education Policy 2020*. . Ministry of Education.
9. Shane, S. (2003). *A general theory of entrepreneurship: The individual–opportunity nexus*. Edward Elgar Publishing.